

UNDERSTANDING THE IMPACT OF PERSONNEL QUALIFICATIONS ON JOB PERFORMANCE IN RESPECT OF SECRET REGISTRY PERSONNEL UNIT'S FILE MINUTING COMMUNICATION IN NORTH EASTERN NIGERIA

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Abstract

In today's competitive work place environment, both public and private organizations are constantly striving to improve their performance and meet the evolving needs of their customers and members of the public as the case may be. At the heart of this pursuit lies the employees of an organization, who play a crucial role in achieving organizational goals and objectives. Effective job performance is crucial for the success of any organization and could be influenced by the qualifications of its personnel. This study explored the impact of personnel qualifications on job performance using Secret Registry personnel Unit's file minuting communication in North East Nigeria: Case Study of FCET Potiskum, FCET Gombe, COE, Zing and COE, Azare. The study adopts Quantitative Research Method using Questionnaire Design with Expectancy theory of performance Management as its theoretical framework. The study revealed that qualifications of staff of Secret Registry of Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria do influence their job performance as staff with higher qualifications perform better than those with lower qualifications. The study recommends that Colleges of Education should recruit staff with higher qualifications to man their Secret Registry for improved job performance.

Keywords: *Personnel qualifications, Job performance, Secret Registry, File minuting communication and Impact.*

Introduction

In today's competitive work place environment, organizations are constantly striving to improve their performance to meet the evolving needs of their customers. At the heart of this pursuit lies the employees of an organization, who play crucial roles in achieving organizational goals and objectives. Effective job performance is key to the success of any organization as it enhances the productivity of the organization. Educational qualifications also

enhance people understanding of the work environment, hence, could lead to job performance at public work place, especially in Colleges of Education in Nigeria.

Conceptual Clarification

Basically, some conceptual clarifications are presented and explained below:

Personnel qualifications: This refers to the educational qualifications of the working class. In this context, it refers to qualifications of Secret Registry staff of Colleges of Education in Nigeria.

Job performance: This refers to the entire value contributed to an organisation by an individual's behavior patterns over a specific period. It indicates how well an individual is fulfilling the job demands. In this context, It refers to the degree of accomplishment of the tasks that make up an individual's job in the Secret Registry of Colleges of Education in Nigeria.

Secret Registry: This refers to confidential office where confidential records are stored and retrieved including confidential files containing personal credentials and disciplinary issues. In this context, it refers to confidential office of Colleges of Education in Nigeria.

File minuting communication: This is an organizational communication in/on a file. In this context, it refers to communication in the file in Colleges of Education in Nigeria.

Impact: This refers to the mark of effect or influence on an action. Here, it refers to the influence of qualifications on job performances of staff of Secret Registry of Colleges of Education in Nigeria.

Conceptual Background

Since educational qualification has long been considered as one of the key predictor of job performance, the administrative staff of Colleges of Education in Nigeria cannot be left behind. This study aims at determining the relationship between educational qualifications and job performance among staff of Secret Registry in the four colleges in North Eastern Nigeria.

The College of Education system is a peculiar organization. It is essentially one of the tertiary education; that is, an academic community, an institution where ideas are generated where high standards are set and maintained. Her staff comprises of the Academic and Non-teaching personnel. While the Academic staff are directly responsible for teaching and research, the Non-teaching staff are responsible for the day-to-day supportive services for the smooth running of the system. The non-teaching staff are grouped into departments like: Provostry, Registry, Bursary, Works and Services, Health, Sports, Information Technology and Resource Centre and Support services in Academic Leadership Offices like Deanery, Departments, Directorates, Units and Library.

The day-to day administrative work of Colleges of Education is directly the responsibility of the Registry Department, statutorily accountable to the Registrar. For staff of the Registry Department to contribute to the smooth running of the College, such Registry staff must be intelligent men and women themselves. They must be professionally and academically qualified for their jobs in order to cope with the academic nature of the College administration. The problem of this study is that, it is known that Secret Registry is meant to keep individual confidential matters that are not supposed to be expose to non-authorized persons. These files are often referred to as “confidential files”. These offices are often restricted as “out of bound” to indicate that it is not open to unauthorized persons. The officers working in this office are often trusted staff that cannot disclose any information about someone without prior approval by an authorized officer.

However, in most Colleges of Education in Nigeria, the staff posted to Secret Registry are often junior staff or intermediate staff or sometimes a senior Executive Cadre staff. This seems to pass the impression that staff with high qualification are not needed in this office. That is why this study intends to find out whether qualification can contribute to the performance of the staff of Secret Registry or not.

The purpose of this study is therefore, to determine the connection between educational qualifications and job performance among staff of Secret Registry in Colleges of Education in Nigeria. specifically to find out the extent to which high qualification contribute to high performance of staff of Secret Registry; the extent to which low qualification contribute to low performance of staff; the level of effectiveness of the performance of staff of Secret Registry; and the level of engagement of staff of Secret Registry in other assignments apart from Secret Registry Job.

The above purposes could be achieved through asking such questions like: to what extent does high qualification contribute to high performance of staff of Secret Registry?; to what extent does low qualification contribute to low performance of staff of Secret Registry?; how effective is the performance of staff of Secret Registry?; as well as do you do other assignments apart from Secret Registry Job?

Literature Review

Scholars have tried to explain educational qualifications, job performance, performance appraisal, Registry as well as file communication. For instance, Stoffberg, Ferreira & Twum-Darko (2023), explained that educational qualification refers to the type and level of qualifications obtained by employees of an organization.

Motowidlo (2003), defines Job performance as the entire value contributed to an organisation by an individual's behavior patterns over a specific period.

Bagul (2014), defines Performance appraisal as a method of evaluating the behavior of employees in the work place.

Yakusak (2021), explains that Registry is a place where official records are kept or a book or system for keeping an official record of items. He classified registry into two, (1) Open Registry and (2) Secret Registry.

Registry according to Kailes and Enders (2014), is a place where official records are kept, or a book or system for keeping an official record of items. Registry data items can be things, e.g motor vehicles, personnel, etc.

Kumije, et al (2023), opine that the Registry department of a University is vested with the responsibility of coordinating various departments, units or sections of the University to ensure efficiency and optimal performance as Registry staff are posted to all faculties, Departments, Sections and Units of the University.

Yakusak (2021), identifies functions of a Registry as follows:

The registry is mainly in charge of (i) storage of files (personal, open, secret (policy) and confidential) (ii) storing, retrieving and tracking of files (iii) management of records (iv) documentation of records (v) receiving and filing of mails.

File content to Gambo and Manu (2021), means a collection of papers on a specific subject matter, which is recognized from a specific serial number, or a file number, and has many correspondence notes, and an appendix to correspondent.

Gambo and Manu (2021), also explain that file communication is like file minuting in an organization, hence, an organisational communication in a file.

Recent empirical studies have demonstrated some significant influence of educational qualification on job performance. For instance, Stoffberg, Ferreira & Twum-Darko (2023), use Individual Work Performance Questionnaire to study the relevance of educational qualification to job performance among academic administrators at a University and their findings revealed that educational qualification is an important predictor of the performance of people at work as for many years, university graduates with bachelor's or master's degrees have been in high demand in the employment market because of their high job productivity.

Additionally, Kumije, et al (2023), study on Registry department and the Nigerian universities: a synthetic analysis using content analysis revealed that university registry staff with higher qualification give high job performance for a proper roadmap and guidance towards the accomplishment and ultimate realization of its set goals, vision and mission.

Ng & Feldman (2009), study on how broadly does levels of educational contribute to job performance and Personnel psychology suggest that higher levels of education positively influence the performance of core tasks, creativity and constructive behavior in employees.

The findings of Baeyhan (2005), research on the impact of higher education on job preparedness and performance of Turkish National Police Officers, shows that higher education impacts on job preparedness and job performance.

Motowidlo (2003), findings on his research on job performance reveal that higher educational qualification can lead to high job performance.

However, on the other hand, Ng & Feldman (2009), reported Aris & Timmins (1989), to have claimed that the degree of education acquired by non-technical employees has no bearing on their level of performance.

Methodology

This study used Quantitative Research Design where questionnaire was used as instrument for collecting and collating data from respondents for the purpose of analyzing the relationship between academic qualifications and staff of Secret Registry of Colleges of Education in Nigeria.

This study purposely selected four Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria to represent the eleven Colleges of Education in the area. Among the four Colleges of Education purposely selected FCET, Gombe in Gombe State and FCET, Potiskum in Yobe State are Federal

Colleges while College of Education, Zing in Taraba State and Aminu Sale College of Education, Azare in Bauchi State are State Colleges of Education.

The population of the study was 65 Secret Registry staff of all the eleven Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria. The study used Raosoft sample size calculator and a response distribution of 50%, a confidence level of 95% and an error level of 5% where a sampled population of 32 was used. Random sampling technique was used to select the 32 sampled population.

Theoretical Framework

This study used Expectancy Theory of Performance Management. Expectancy theory was formulated by Victor Vroom in 1964. It is based on the premise that individuals are motivated to exert efforts when they believe that their efforts will lead to desired outcomes.

According to this theory, employees' motivation and performance are influenced by three key factors: expectancy, instrumentality, and valence.

Expectancy refers to the belief that putting in effort will result in achieving the desired level of performance.

Instrumentality is the belief that successful performance will lead to desired outcomes such as rewards or recognition.

Valence is the value an individual places on the outcomes or rewards associated with job performance. This theory suggests that for employees to be motivated to perform well, they must believe that their efforts will lead to desired outcomes, and these outcomes must be valued by them.

The theory becomes relevant because this study is trying to see how it can link possessing high qualification to its influence on high job performance through expectancy, instrumentality and valence.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table One: Qualification Distribution

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
0' Level	4	12.5
ND/NCE	6	18.75
HND	2	6.25
First Degree	16	50
Master's Degree	4	12.5
PhD	-	-
Total	32	100

Table One above indicates that there are 16 first degree holders working under Secret Registry in the four sampled Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria, representing 50%, six NCE/ND holders representing 18.75%, four staff each holding Master's Degree and 0' level each representing 12.5% as well as two staff with HND representing 6.25% respectively.

Table Two: Availability of Schedule of Duty

Availability of Schedule of Duty	Frequency	Percentage
Available	20	62.5
Not Available	12	37.5
Total	32	100

Table Two indicates that 20 Secret Registry staff in the four sampled Colleges have their schedule of duties, representing 62.5% while 12 of them do not have schedule of duties, representing 37.5% respectively.

Table Three: Encountered Leakage of Official Information from Secret Registry Staff with High Qualifications

Category of Leaked Confidential Information Staff	Frequency	Percentage
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Ever Encountered Leaked Confidential Information from High Qualification Holders	-	-
Never Encountered Leaked Confidential Information from High Qualification Holders	22	100
Neutral	-	-
Total	22	100

Table Three above shows that Registry of Colleges of Education in the North Eastern Nigeria have never receive complaints of leaked confidential information from all the 22 sampled Secret Registry staff with high qualifications, representing 100%.

Table Four: Encountered Leakage of Official Information from Secret Registry Staff with Low Qualifications

Category of Leaked Confidential Information Staff	Frequency	Percentage
Ever Encountered Leaked Confidential Information from Low Qualification Holders	2	20
Never Encountered from Low Qualification Holders	8	80
Neutral	-	-
Total	10	100

Table Four above shows that the Registrars and Management of Colleges of Education in the North Eastern Nigeria have never receive complaints of leaked confidential information from eight of the sampled ten Secret Registry staff with low qualifications, representing 80% while they have received complaints of leaked confidential information from two out of the ten Secret Registry staff with low qualifications, representing 20%.

Table Five: Effectiveness of Job Performance

Effectiveness of Job Performance	Frequency	Percentage
Have Awards	-	-
Have Commendation Letters	-	-

Above Average Ratings	-	-
All of the Above	24	75
None of the Above	8	25
Total	32	100

Table Five above indicates that 24 of the sampled 32 Secret Registry staff in the North Eastern Colleges of Education are effective in their job performances, representing 75% while eight of them are not effective, representing 25% respectively.

Table Six: Effective Secret Registry Staff with high qualifications

Effectiveness of Staff	Frequency	Percentage
Effective	20	90.91
Not Effective	-	-
Neutral	2	9.09
Total	22	100

Table six above indicates that 20 of the sampled 22 Colleges of Education in the North Eastern Nigeria Secret Registry staff with high qualifications are effective in their job performances, representing 90.91% while two of them are not effective, representing 9.09% respectively.

Table Seven: Effective Secret Registry Staff with low qualifications

Effectiveness of Staff	Frequency	Percentage
Effective	2	20
Not Effective	8	80
Neutral	-	-
Total	10	100

Table Seven above indicates that eight of the sampled ten Secret Registry staff with low qualifications in Colleges of Education in the North Eastern Nigeria are not effective in their job performances, representing 80% while two of them are effective, representing 20% respectively.

Table Eight: Additional Assignment

Additional Assignments	Frequency	Percentage
Additional Work Outside Schedule of Duty	-	-
Work Under Stress	-	-
Work Under Crises	-	-
Being Creative and Initiative	-	-
Learning and Adapting very Fast	-	-
All of the Above	22	68.75
None of the Above	6	18.75
Neutral	4	12.5
Total	32	100

Table Eight above shows that 22 of the sampled 32 Colleges of Education in the North Eastern Nigeria Secret Registry staff do additional assignments to their schedule of duty by working under stress and crises, being creative, being initiative, learning and adapting very fast, representing 68.75%, six of them only rely on their schedules of duty, representing 18.75% while four of them are placed on neutral grounds, representing 12.25% respectively.

Table Nine: High Qualification Yielding High Job Performance

High Qualification Yielding High Job Performance	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	30	93.75
No	-	-
Neutral	2	2.65
Total	32	100

Table Nine above reveals that 30 out of the 32 respondents agreed that high qualification yields effective job performance, representing 93.75% while two of them remained neutral, representing 2.65% respectively.

Table Ten: High Qualification Yielding Low Job Performance

High Qualification Yielding Low Job Performance	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	-	-
No	30	93.75
Neutral	2	6.25
Total	32	100

Table Ten above reveals that 30 out of the 32 respondents agreed that high qualification does not yield low job performance, representing 93.75% while two of them remained neutral, representing 2.65% respectively.

Table Eleven: Low Qualification Yielding High Job Performance

Low Qualification Yielding High Job Performance	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	2	6.25
No	28	87.5
Neutral	2	6.25
Total	32	100

Table Eleven above reveals that 28 out of the 32 respondents did not agreed that low qualification yields effective job performance, representing 87.5%, two of them agreed that low qualification yields effective job performance, representing 6.25% while two of them remained neutral, representing 2.65% respectively.

Table Twelve: Low Qualification Yielding Low Job Performance

Low Qualification Yielding Low Job Performance	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	30	93.75

No	-	-
Neutral	2	6.25
Total	32	100

Table Twelve above reveals that 30 out of the 32 respondents agreed that low qualification yields low job performance, representing 93.75% while two of them remained neutral, representing 2.65% respectively.

Findings

Based on the tables above, the followings form the major findings of this study: That there are more staff with high qualifications now working in the Secret Registry in Colleges of Education in the North Eastern Nigeria than those with low qualifications.

Staff of Colleges of Education in North East Nigeria that have their schedule of duties that they work with are more than those that do not have.

Registry of Colleges of Education in the North Eastern Nigeria have not receive complaints of leaked confidential information from Secret Registry staff with high qualifications.

Registry of Colleges of Education in the North Eastern Nigeria have received two complaints of leaked confidential information from Secret Registry staff with low qualifications which is negligible.

Many of the Secret Registry staff of Registry of Colleges of Education in the North Eastern Nigeria are effective in their job performance.

Majority of the Secret Registry staff of Registry of Colleges of Education in the North Eastern Nigeria with high qualifications are effective in their job performance.

Majority of Secret Registry staff of Colleges of Education in the North Eastern Nigeria with low qualifications are not effective in their job performance.

Majority of Secret Registry staff of Colleges of Education in the North Eastern Nigeria do additional assignments to their schedule of duty by working under stress and crises, being creative, being initiative and learning and adapting very fast.

Majority of the respondents agreed that high qualification yields effective job performance.

Majority of the respondents agreed that low qualification yields low job performance.

Conclusion

Based on the findings above, it can be concluded that schedules of duty is available for staff working in the Secret Registry in Colleges of Education in the North Eastern Nigeria. There are just minimal and negligible cases of leaking of confidential information from staff of Secret Registry in Colleges of Education in the North Eastern Nigeria. Secret Registry staff with higher qualifications working in Colleges of Education in the North Eastern Nigeria are effective in their job performance while those with low qualifications do not perform optimally.

Based on the above facts, it can be concluded that personnel qualifications play critical roles in determining the job performance of employees in Secret Registry of Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria. Possession of higher qualifications by staff of Secret Registry often expose them to wider experience so that they can contribute towards achieving organizational goals for their Colleges outside their schedules. Possession of higher qualifications by staff of Secret Registry do contributes to reduction in cases of leaking of confidential information.

Recommendations

Based on the findings available by the study and the conclusion thus drawn, the following recommendations are hereby made:

- i. Since possession of high qualification yields effective job performance while low qualification yields low job performance, Management of Colleges of Education in Nigeria should carefully recruit people with high qualifications to man Secret Registry of their Colleges;
- ii. However, where the College already has low qualification staff working for it, these staff should be sponsored to obtain higher qualifications and be adequately motivated to enable them work towards achieving organizational goals;
- iii. Colleges of Education in North East Nigeria should make sure that all their staff of Secret Registry have their schedules of duty to work with;
- iv. Registry of Colleges of Education in the North Eastern Nigeria should put machinery in place to curtail the few cases of complaints of leaking confidential information from Secret Registry staff who are saddled with the responsibility of keeping confidential records of the Colleges.

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